

CITY UNIVERSITY OF MOGADISHU

A CAPSTONE RESEARCH PROJECT

ON

PHISHING ATTACK AWARENESS AMONG SOMALI UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

PRESENTED TO:

THE DEPARTMENT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (IT)
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BY

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DECLARATION

I am Abdullahi Ahmed Mohamud, solemnly declare that this research is not a reproduction of another person's work. I did this entire research project and I duly acknowledged the sources of information.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this capstone research project meets the partial requirement for the award of the degree of Bachelor of information technology (IT) by City University of Mogadishu.

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ABSTRACT

Phishing attacks remain a significant cybersecurity threat, particularly among university students, who are often targeted with fake scholarship emails and fraudulent internship offers. This study aims to assess phishing awareness among Somali undergraduate students and identify strategies to reduce their vulnerability. A mixed-method approach was used, including a social experiment and interviews. The social experiment involved distributing fake scholarship links to evaluate participants' behavior, while interviews with cybersecurity experts provided deeper insights. Data were analyzed to identify trends, common vulnerabilities, and effective countermeasures.

The social experiment showed that 98% of participants clicked on phishing links, even though they were aware of phishing risks. The majority of participants were Master's degree applicants (86%), with a slightly higher proportion of male participants (51%) compared to females (49%). The experiment revealed significant differences in phishing susceptibility among different universities, with varying response rates observed. These results underscore the importance of improving students' cautious behavior when interacting with online content.

Interviews with cybersecurity experts revealed that students' awareness of phishing attacks is generally low to moderate. Foundational knowledge, such as recognizing phishing emails or using MFA, was limited, especially among non-IT students. Experts emphasized the need for practical training, real-world simulations, and tailored awareness campaigns to address these gaps. Advanced technologies like AI, MFA, and endpoint detection systems were recommended to enhance protection.

In conclusion, this study recommends universities implement mandatory cybersecurity training, real-world phishing simulations, and enforce technical measures like MFA. Raising awareness and adopting user-friendly security practices can significantly reduce students' susceptibility to phishing attacks and create a safer online environment.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Phishing is a type of online fraud where attackers try to trick people into giving away their personal information, such as passwords, credit card details, or bank account numbers. This is often done through fake emails, messages, or websites that look like they are from trusted companies.

A phishing attack is a type of online fraud that aims to steal sensitive information from a victim. The rate at which technology is developing nowadays is drastically altering how people work and live their daily lives. Email and the internet have grown in importance in people's lives as a result of technology's rising popularity. The swift adoption of technology developments has led to a notable surge in computer security threats, hence elevating the susceptibility of human exploitation. Phishing is one type of computer security attack that has grown to be a deadly security risk. An attempt to get sensitive information, usually in the form of usernames, passwords, credit card numbers, bank account information, or other critical data, with the intention of using or selling the information, is referred to as "phishing". Phishing attacks aim to obtain confidential data or financial information by deceiving a user into divulging it on a fraudulent website. Pronouncing "phishing" as "fishing" (Alazab and Broadhurst, 2016).

Phishing is the practice of an attacker attempting to deceive a victim into divulging private account information or other online login credentials. Phishing tests can be a useful tool in employee cybersecurity training. Phishing simulations can have many benefits, including: Measuring vulnerability: Phishing simulations can help measure the degrees of corporate and employee vulnerability. Increasing user alertness: Phishing simulations can help increase user alertness to phishing risks. Improving cybersecurity: Phishing simulation training and services can improve an organization's cybersecurity by reinforcing the human layer of protection. Decreasing fraudulent activity: Phishing simulations with appropriate reporting procedures can decrease the chances of fraudulent activity. Teaching employees to recognize phishing emails: Phishing simulations can help employees learn how to recognize phishing emails and avoid falling for them. Preventing data breaches: Phishing simulations and testing can help prevent data breaches. To further investigate the role of all the variables of interest, a Generalized Linear Model (GLM) analysis was conducted.

Phishing is a type of online fraud where attackers try to trick people into giving away their personal information, such as passwords, credit card details, or bank account numbers. This is often done through fake emails, messages, or websites that look like they are from trusted companies (“Phishing attacks,” 2017). According to Kumaraguru, Rhee, Sheng, Hasan, Acquisti, Cranor, and Hong (2007), In order to help internet users avoid opening phishing emails, academics that study anti-phishing have created a number of methods to stop and identify phishing attempts. The development of techniques to make users less vulnerable to phishing assaults has received less attention than the abundance of work done on assisting users in identifying phishing websites.

The more people connect to the virtual world, the more opportunities there are for cybercriminals to take advantage of them. Despite efforts to reduce these dangers through technological advancements, human error remains the "weakest link" in cyber security (Mayhorn, Welk, Zielinska, & Murphy-Hill, 2015). In an effort to hack, spread malware, or obtain personal information, fraudsters use techniques like "spam," "phishing," or "spear phishing," which focus more on the victim's judgement than on their virtual protection measures (Gratian, Bandi, Cukier, Dykstra, & Ginther, 2018). Spam emails are a typical way for malware to spread. In addition to benign advertising sent by unsolicited emails, SMS texts, or social media messages, spam can also include malware or viruses that are intended to steal confidential or personal data from its users. Even though spam might not seem like much on an individual basis, estimates show that in January 2018, there were 422 billion spam messages sent globally on average every day, accounting for over 85% of all daily email traffic.

A college student's level of user education can help identify whether or not they are more susceptible to phishing emails. A study, done by Alseadoon, Chan, Foo, and Nieto (2012), showed that younger members were more susceptible to these kinds of attacks, mostly because they were less comfortable with technology, less at ease using the internet, and had not had much phishing training. When attackers try to infiltrate, spread malware, or steal personal information by using spam, phishing, or spear-phishing techniques information, they go after their victim's discretion instead of their virtual defenses. Chaudhry, Chaudhry and Rittenhouse (2016), imply that the three components of a classic phishing assault are a lure, a hook, and a catch.

Convincing recipients to reveal sensitive information comes next, after they are persuaded, the correspondence is genuine. The success of the deception is aided by a number of social

manipulators, including liking or trusting the email source, implying reciprocity (e.g., returning favours) or "social proof" (i.e., others are participating), expressing scarcity, or citing an authoritative source. Phishing emails are considered to be "spear phishing" when they incorporate individualized data in their lures. Spear-phishing emails frequently include material that certain receivers might find significant or familiar (De Kimpe et al. 2018).

Attackers invest time gathering personal data that is pertinent to specific users in order to get such data, which they subsequently utilize to create phone emails (Caputo et al. 2014). These emails typically pretend to be from reputable businesses, reliable connections, or situations that are personally significant to the recipient (De Kimpe et al. 2018). 117 college students were given a series of emails that were either spear-phishing, phishing, or authentic in order to assess the impact of various social engineering techniques. According to the findings, students were less adept at identifying spear-phishing attempts than general phishing attempts and had a tendency to characterize emails as authentic rather than fraudulent. A common lure is an email message that looks to be from a reliable source, and it takes advantage of the following to increase its credibility: Curiosity: emails with hacked links that seem to take users to videos of current affairs or events; Fear: emails from the "bank" asking users to confirm their information after account breaches; Empathy: emails pretending to be from friends or family in need of money or personal information. Students were less able to recognize spear-phishing emails when they employed an authority-style social engineering tactic, meaning the email's purported sender had control over the recipient Butavicius et al (2015).

1.2 Problem statement

Phishing simulators are a fantastic method to assess your organization's cyber resiliency in addition to one-on-one training. You can determine which data is most vulnerable to attack, find out where general training needs to be improved, and get your company ready for the most common kinds of attacks.

Phishing attacks present significant challenges due to their evolving and deceptive nature. These attacks are increasingly sophisticated, making them difficult to identify and combat effectively. Attackers often mimic trusted brands or individuals, creating highly convincing fake communications that are challenging for users to distinguish from legitimate ones. A critical

challenge is the lack of user awareness, as many individuals fail to recognize phishing tactics or understand the importance of verifying links and emails before taking action.

Since the majority of these phishers are able to conceal the location of their servers and operate almost anonymously, they are also difficult to stop. Even users with top-notch security tools are susceptible to phishing attacks as, in most cases, they rely only on data entered into forms rather than computer viruses. Although it can appear simple to prevent, phishing scams are becoming more difficult for victims to recognize due to advancements in the phishing community.

1.3 Research objectives

1. To find the level of awareness about phishing attacks among Somali undergraduate students.
2. To find the most common phishing techniques targeting university students in Somalia.
3. To find strategies for improving phishing awareness among Somali undergraduate students.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the current level of awareness about phishing attacks among Somali undergraduate students?
2. What are the most common phishing techniques targeting university students in Somalia?
3. What strategies can be implemented to improve phishing awareness among Somali undergraduate students?

1.5 Significance

The results of this study will help raise awareness of phishing attacks in Somali universities and will also furnish current information for future researchers and students attempting to further develop this research with their own distinct perspectives.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Phishing is described as "an attempt or criminally and fraudulently acquire sensitive information, such as usernames, passwords and credit card details, by masquerading as a trustworthy entity in an electronic communication"(Wikipedia, 2008).

The Gartner report (Litan, 2007) notes that Phishing attacks are become more frequent, stealthier, and frequently intended to infect computers with software that takes user passwords and other data." The conclusions of the Gartner study are supported by trends disclosed by Symantec. During the first half of 2007, the Symantec Probe Network discovered 196,860 unique phishing messages, or an average of 1,088 new messages per day, an increase of 18% over 2006. Over the same period, its network stopped 12.5 million phishing mails on average per day, up 53% from the year before (Symantec Internet Security Threat Report: Trends for January-June 2007, 2007). According to the Gartner study, which is indicative of adult internet users in the United States, 124 million respondents said they had either certainly received or thought they got a phishing email, which is a 118% rise in only three years. According to the survey, during the year that ended in August of 2007, each participant had received an average of around 80 phishing emails (Litan, 2007).

Furthermore, according to the Gartner survey, 3.3% of the participants (3.6 million) believed or were positive that they had received phishing emails and suffered financial harm, up from 23.6% in 2006. However, the average loss per incident was \$886 in 2007 as opposed to \$1,244 in 2006, and 16. million people were able to recover 64% of their losses, which was an increase from 15. million people's 54% recovery in 2006. However, \$3.2 billion was lost to phishing in 2007 as a result of the rise in assaults (Litan, 2007) up \$500 million from 2006 (Keizer, 2007).

The majority of phishing techniques involve link manipulation, also known as technical disguising, to route users to the phisher's website by using a subdomain or a slightly changed or masked URL. The "@" sign in a link can successfully trick the user into thinking that another URL will be opened

because the server doesn't recognize any characters that come before the @. Phishers can outsmart anti-phishing software by employing file evasion, which involves utilizing graphics in emails instead of text (Recognize Phishing Scams and Fraudulent Emails, 2008; Wikipedia, 2008).

Cross-site scripting is a more advanced kind of online forgery (CSS or XSS). Using this technique, a hacker locates vulnerabilities on corporate websites that allow for script change. When a person logs onto the website, the phisher can then take over a valid session. A user receives an email from the phisher enticing them to visit a genuine website. The phisher steals personal data from the user when they log onto the website (Krebs, 2006).

Social engineering may also be used in phishing. By pretending to be a reliable person (a new hire, a support person, or a boss), the phisher may be able to get information from the user and may even display credentials. Social skills, or the ability to communicate with people, are used to gather knowledge piece by piece from people until enough is gathered to endanger a system (National Cyber Alert System Cyber Security Tip ST04-014, 2007).

2.2 Global Context of Phishing Attacks

Worldwide, there were at least 72,758 distinct phishing attacks. Compared to the 123,486 attacks reported in 2H2012, this is much fewer. The drop is the result of fewer phishing attempts that compromised several domains simultaneously by using shared virtual servers. A phishing site that targets a particular brand or organization is called an assault. For example, a single domain name can be the target of multiple distinct phishing campaigns directed towards various banks. 53,685 distinct domain names were the target of the attacks. Once more, because there have been fewer instances of virtual server hacking, fewer domains are being used than in the second half of 2012.

From 258 million in November 2012 to 261 million in April 2013, there were 261 million domain names registered worldwide.³ Furthermore, 1,972 assaults against 1,626 IP addresses as opposed to domain names were found. (At <http://142.234.140.62/pay/jian>, for instance) For three and a half years, the quantity of IP-based attacks has not changed. There were no reports of any phishes using IPv6 addresses. We found 12,173 domain names that we think were registered maliciously by phishers out of the 53,685 phishing domains. Compared to 2,835 in H 2012, this is twice as many.

In Somalia the last six months, phishing and vishing attacks have been the most common cyber-attacks on telecom organizations in Somalia, accounting for 75% of them. Following the increased

usage of the Internet throughout the world and the digitization of numerous government operations and procedures, cybersecurity has emerged as a national concern in Somalia. Cybercriminals utilize the internet to target government assets that are secret in order to compromise vital infrastructure, steal data, or obtain personal information from residents. There are a number of reasons why these criminals are targeting the infrastructure of the Somali government, including but not limited to financial gain or giving intelligence to enemies (Sambuli et al., 2015).

There are currently no national cybersecurity guidelines or standards, frameworks, regulations, or awareness campaigns in Somalia. It is among the least cybersecure nations, which shows that there is a significant disconnect between national cybersecurity plans and international norms. Regarding cybersecurity, the nation also lacks programs for education and training. Specifically, there isn't a platform that informs citizens about cybersecurity concerns. This is due to the perception that internet users' insecure online activity is a result of their lack of knowledge (Thomson et al., 2006).

This is because an increased amount of effort is being directed towards occurrences rather than prevention, which would lead to a decrease in the quantity of events reported. The lack of assignor for the thesis serves as evidence of how little attention is paid to cybersecurity in Somalia, particularly with regard to cybersecurity awareness, which highlights the growing necessity for this research. This indicates a research deficit in Somalia, therefore in order to carry out pertinent actions, Somalia must have a complete grasp of the country's present cybersecurity knowledge level. There is currently just one published study that examines cybersecurity knowledge in Somalia, and it focuses on university students in Mogadishu (Warshaddaha, 2019).

In comparison, the average uptime in 2H2012 was 26 hours and 13 minutes, whereas in 1H2013 it was 44 hours and 39 minutes. Compared to the previous low median of 5 hours and 45 minutes in 1H2012, the median uptime in 1H2013 was 12 hours and 52 minutes, more than twice as long. There were 195 top-level domains (TLDs) where phishing was reported, but only three TLDs—.COM,.TK, and.INFO—accounted for 82% of malicious domain registrations. Compared to the 611 targeted institutions identified in 2H2012, we counted 720 target institutions, a significant increase. The percentage of domain names used for phishing that contained a brand name or variant was only 2.3%.

2.3 Challenges phishing attacks

The problem with phishing is that attackers constantly look for new and creative ways to fool users into believing their actions involve a legitimate website or email. Phishers have become more skilled at forging websites to appear identical to the expected location, even including logos and graphics in the phishing emails to strengthen their persuasiveness. Dangerous new sophisticated phishing techniques are being used, and they make use of publicly accessible personal information to create realistic assaults that go straight after victims. Techniques like context-aware phishing and social phishing are prime instances of how attackers are making use of the vast quantity of public data at their disposal to make their con games more convincing.

Certain phishing attempts go so far as to insert malware, such as trojans or worms, within the emails they send. This compromises the victim's computer's security and gives the attackers another tool with which to choose targets and launch attacks. Additionally, phishers are beginning to use psychology in their emails to prey on feelings of trust, greed, or haste. When combined with the authentic appearance and feel of the spoof websites, such attacks can even affect more careful and observant consumers.

2.4 Prevention Strategies and Solutions

Phishing can be stopped before it reaches the user either by blacklisting or blocking phishing sites or by filtering out phishing emails. The first method is carried out by looking at the URLs and the sites that they claim to be, either manually or automated through the use of machine learning. Although this may catch some sites, there is little hope of catching all of them, since a phisher can easily just make a new site once one is taken down.

If the second strategy is successful, it will prevent the user from ever seeing the connection to the phishing websites, making it seem like a more effective approach. Email servers employ a large number of effective spam filters, but few phishing filters because of their complexity.

Additionally, machine learning approaches are being used to create filters against phishing. The authors of "Classification of Phishing Email Using Random Forest Machine Learning Technique" go into the traits that are utilized to categorize phishing emails.

Identifying potential phishing sites or warning users to avoid visiting malicious websites (or providing malicious information in these emails or sites) even after they have received and viewed malicious emails are two strategies used by attackers to ensure that phishing emails and websites reach unsuspecting users. Numerous web browsers come equipped with built-in protections against phishing websites, which can be identified by either an active or passive signal. Passive indicators do not interfere with the user's task, whereas active indicators notify users through pop-up windows that the website they are visiting is a suspected forgery or is not deemed safe. Make use of anti-phishing techniques and technology that are able to identify and stop phone emails and websites. By putting up a barrier between your computer and the attacker, firewalls are a useful tool for preventing external attacks. When combined, desktop and network firewalls can improve security and lower the likelihood of a hacker breaking into your system.

Change passwords frequently. If you have any online accounts, you should make it a practice to change your passwords on a frequent basis to keep an attacker from getting unrestricted access. It's possible that your accounts have been compromised without you knowing, therefore changing your passwords on a regular basis will help to keep criminals out and avoid further attempts. Refrain from giving in to those pop-ups. Not only are pop-ups annoying, but they are frequently connected to malware in phishing attempts. You may now download and install free ad-blocking software on most browsers, which will automatically prevent the majority of dangerous pop-ups. But if someone does manage to get past the ad-blocker, resist the urge to click! Sometimes pop-ups will attempt to trick you into thinking that the "Close" button is somewhere else, so always try to check for a "x" in one of the corners.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the research design, population, sampling methods, data collection instruments, and data analysis techniques used to investigate the level of phishing attack awareness among Somali undergraduate students. It also discusses the ethical considerations and limitations of the study.

3.2 Research designs

The study adopts a mixed-methods research design, combining a social experiment and interviews. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected to assess the level of phishing attack awareness among Somali undergraduate students. According to Creswell (2014), mixed-methods research allows for the triangulation of data, enhancing the validity and reliability of the study by using both numerical data (from the social experiment) and narrative data (from the interviews).

These methods are appropriate for gathering comprehensive data on students' awareness and behaviors related to phishing attacks.

3.3 Research Population

The target population for this study includes undergraduate students enrolled in 9 universities namely Banadir university, City university of Mogadishu, Hormuud university, Jamhuria university, Jobkey university, Simad university, Siu, Somaville, University of Somalia in Mogadishu, Somalia with a particular focus on final-year students. Final-year students are chosen because they are more likely to have significant exposure to technology and online communication, making them an ideal group for analyzing phishing awareness.

3.4 Sample size

The sample size was drawn from the population and it was 50 participants collected from social experiment data and 6 participants who key informants were interviewed to collect additional data on the phishing attack.

3.5 Sampling Techniques

- **Purposive Sampling:** Purposive sampling refers to a group of non-probability sampling techniques in which units are selected because they have characteristics that you need in your sample. In other words, units are selected "on purpose" in purposive sampling (Nikolopoulou, 2022). Participants were selected based on specific criteria, including being final-year students from different universities and degree programs in Somalia.
- The sample consisted of 50 participants, ensuring diversity in terms of university affiliation, academic discipline, and gender.

3.6 Data Collection Methods

the study used both Quantitative and qualitative data collection methods to capture a comprehensive view of phishing awareness:

3.6.1 Quantitative data collection method (Social Experiment)

- A simulated phishing attack was conducted to assess students' Awareness to phishing Messages and their responses to such attacks.
- **Tools Used:**
 - A phishing message template was crafted to mimic a fake scholarship offer, utilizing urgent and persuasive language to increase engagement.
 - A mock website, resembling an official scholarship application portal, was created to deceive participants into entering personal information.
 - Tracking tools were employed to monitor link clicks and data submissions.
 - A form was used to collect additional data from participants.
- **Procedure:**
 - Informed consent was obtained from participants via WhatsApp before sending the phishing links. They were informed about the study's purpose, their voluntary participation, and the confidentiality of their data.
 - The phishing message was distributed to participants via WhatsApp, including a link to the fake scholarship website.

- Participants' responses (link clicks and data submissions) were recorded.
- After the Social experiment, participants were debriefed to ensure no harm or misuse of data occurred, and to provide them with insights into phishing techniques.

3.6.2 Qualitative Data Collection (Key informant interview)

After the social experiment, structured interviews were conducted with a group of six cybersecurity experts. The purpose of these interviews was to gain deeper insights into the interpretation of the social experiment results and to explore expert opinions on improving phishing awareness and cybersecurity training for students. The experts were provided with the results of the social experiment prior to the interview to inform their responses and allow for a more detailed discussion.

3.7 Data Analysis Techniques

The data collected was analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods:

3.7.1 Quantitative Analysis

- Descriptive statistics (e.g., percentages,) were used to summarize the social experiment results.
- The data was presented in aggregate form to provide an overview of participants' behavior during the social experiment, such as the number of clicks on phishing links and the rate of personal data submissions.

3.7.2 Qualitative Analysis

- The data from the structured interviews with cybersecurity experts were analyzed using content analysis. The first step in the analysis involved transcribing the interviews to capture all verbal responses accurately. These transcripts were then carefully color-coded to highlight recurring themes, key ideas, and significant patterns in the experts' responses.
- Following the coding process, a detailed content analysis was conducted to identify and categorize the emerging themes related to the social experiment results. This analysis focused on understanding the experts' interpretations of the findings, their views on students' vulnerability to phishing, and their recommendations for improving cybersecurity awareness and training.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

The following ethical protocols were followed to ensure the study met ethical standards:

- **Informed Consent:** Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, their rights, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Consent was obtained via WhatsApp before sending any Social experimental links.
- **Confidentiality:** Participants' responses were anonymized to protect their identities.
- **Debriefing:** After the social experiment, participants were debriefed. They were informed that they had been part of a social experiment aimed at raising awareness about phishing attacks. As part of the debriefing, participants were shown a short educational video on phishing attacks, which provided guidance on how to identify and avoid such threats in the future.

3.9 Limitations of the Study

The study encountered several limitations:

- **Limited Sample Size:** The relatively small sample size (50 participants) may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader population of Somali undergraduate students.
- **Technology Limitations:** The study was constrained by available resources and technology. Certain software tools required for more advanced phishing simulations and data tracking were not accessible due to financial constraints.
- **Limited number of Experts interviewed:** Due to time and resource limitations, only a small group of six experts could be interviewed for the study.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Social Experimental Results

The below social experiment questions are asked to collect the views of 50 participants regarding their awareness of phishing attack.

Table 4.1 1 Total visitors

S.NO	Date	Frequency	Percent
1	04-11-2024	32	33%
2	05-11-2024	5	5%
3	06-11-2024	5	5%
4	07-11-2024	26	26%
5	08-11-2024	23	23%
6	09-11-2024	8	8%
	Total	99	100%

The Social experiment table shows the total number of link clicks (visitors), distributed across six dates. On 04-11-2024, 32 clicks were recorded, making up 33% of the total. On both 05-11-2024 and 06-11-2024, there were 5 clicks each, accounting for 5% each. The remaining days show the following percentages: 07-11-2024 with 26 clicks (26%), 08-11-2024 with 23 clicks (23%), and 09-11-2024 with 8 clicks (8%). The total number of clicks across all dates is 99, representing 100% of the visits.

Out of 99 people who clicked on the fake website links even though they knew about phishing, it shows something important about how people act online. Even when people know about phishing risks, they might still click on these links because of reasons like curiosity, feeling rushed, or not checking if the link is real. This shows that just knowing about the risks isn't enough. We also need to teach people how to stay safe online and keep reminding them of good habits to reduce these mistakes.

Gender of respondents

Table 4.1.2 Gender of respondents

The chart illustrates the gender distribution of respondents, with 51% identified as male and 49% as female. This indicates a nearly equal participation rate between genders, with males slightly outnumbering females. The information shows that men are more likely to fall for phishing attacks. More men than women clicked on phishing links. This means women are a bit more careful or aware in this situation. It's important to focus on helping men because they seem more at risk.

Applying for which degree

Table 4.1.3 Applying for which degree

The Social experiment also analyzed the educational goals of respondents, revealing that 86% of them were applying for a Master's degree (MSc), while 14% were pursuing a Doctoral degree (PhD). This indicates that a significant majority of respondents were Master's degree seekers, which may suggest a higher level of interest or vulnerability among this group when it comes to scholarship opportunities.

University from which BSC Or MSC obtained

Table 4.1.4 University from which BSC Or MSC obtained

S.NO	University	Frequency	Percent
1	Benadir university	7	14%
2	City university	8	16%
3	Hormuud university	6	12%
4	Jamhuria university	5	10%
5	Jobkey university	9	18%
6	Somaville	1	2%
7	Simad university	4	8%

8	University of Somalia	5	10%
9	Siu	4	8%
	Total	49	100.0

Table 4.1.4 University from which BSC Or MSC obtained

The Social experiment targeting fake scholarships revealed varying susceptibility among respondents from different universities. Jobkey University had the highest response rate, accounting for 19%, followed by City University with 17%, Benadir University with 14%, Hormuud University at 12%, and both Jamhuria University and the University of Somalia at 10% each. Simad University and Siu contributed 8% each, while Somaville University had the lowest response rate at 2%. This data highlights notable differences in phishing susceptibility and underscores the need for targeted cybersecurity awareness efforts in higher education institutions.

Table 4.1.5 Desired scholarship degree program

S.NO	Desired	Frequency	Percent
1	Human resource	4	8%
2	Civil engineering	3	6%
3	Cyber security	15	30%
4	Data science	7	14%
5	Artificial intelligence	8	8%
6	International law	4	4%
7	Political science	2	2%
8	Public health	6	12%
	Total	99	100%

Table 4.1.5 Desired scholarship degree program

4.2 Interview results

4.2.1 Demographic information

The participants included 67% males and 33% females. Regarding age, 33% were between 20-25 years old, while 67% were aged 26-35. In terms of specialization, 83% worked directly in the cybersecurity field, and 17% were in a related area. When it comes to experience, 67% had 3-5 years of cybersecurity experience, while 33% had 1-2 years of experience.

4.2.2 The level of cybersecurity awareness among undergraduate students.

Many participants mentioned that the level of cybersecurity awareness among undergraduate students, especially final-year students, is "low to moderate." The understanding of basic threats, such as phishing and using strong passwords, was frequently mentioned. These foundational practices are commonly known, but students often lack the ability to recognize more sophisticated attacks. This basic knowledge may stem from personal experience but is not typically part of formal university education.

A significant portion of responses focused on the limited understanding of advanced cybersecurity concepts. Multi-factor authentication (MFA) and phishing awareness were highlighted as areas where students often lack deeper knowledge. Many participants noted that IT students have more exposure to these topics, while students from non-IT fields only possess surface-level awareness. This means that while they may understand the need for strong passwords or antivirus software, they are not equipped to handle more sophisticated cybersecurity measures that could better protect them from phishing and other advanced attacks.

Most participants agreed that more practical training is needed to improve students' cybersecurity awareness. Practical workshops and real-world threat simulations were emphasized as necessary for building hands-on skills. While students may have a theoretical understanding of basic threats, they often lack the skills to identify and respond to real-world phishing attempts. Practical workshops help students build the skills needed to spot attacks before they fall victim to them.

4.2.3 The effectiveness of cybersecurity awareness campaigns or training programs in reducing phishing attack success rates among institutions is important.

Many participants emphasized that cybersecurity awareness campaigns and training programs are moderately effective, especially when tailored to specific threats like phishing. The success of these programs heavily depends on regular follow-ups and real-world simulations to test preparedness. When training is reinforced and tailored to address real-world scenarios, it significantly improves staff vigilance. Without consistent reinforcement, the effectiveness tends to diminish, as staff may forget or overlook important lessons over time. This suggests that continual updates and practical exercises are key to maintaining the impact of training.

A common theme was the effectiveness of practical exercises, such as phishing simulations, in enhancing the impact of training. Participants mentioned that hands-on exercises, like mock phishing tests or quizzes, help staff better understand and recognize phishing attempts. These interactive elements engage participants more effectively than passive methods, such as sending emails. This highlights that awareness campaigns that actively involve employees in simulated phishing scenarios lead to a more significant reduction in phishing success rates, as they offer practical, real-world experience.

Most participants agreed that while training programs are helpful in recognizing and avoiding common phishing attempts, they have limitations when it comes to advanced or targeted attacks like spear phishing. The need for additional technical measures alongside training was emphasized. This suggests that while awareness campaigns are useful for general phishing defense, they need to be supplemented with more sophisticated security measures to address highly targeted threats. More advanced defense techniques are necessary to ensure comprehensive protection against the full range of phishing attacks.

4.2.4 The latest advancements in technology that can help detect or mitigate phishing attacks are crucial to consider.

Many participants mentioned the use of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to detect phishing attacks. AI-based systems analyze patterns in email content, sender behavior, and website authenticity to identify phishing attempts automatically. These technologies help detect

suspicious emails and fake websites before users can interact with them, improving the overall security posture. The use of AI and ML allows for a proactive, automated approach to catching threats, which is crucial in combating the ever-evolving nature of phishing tactics.

Another frequently mentioned advancement was multi-factor authentication (MFA). MFA strengthens security by adding another layer of verification, such as a text message code or biometric check, making it significantly harder for attackers to misuse stolen credentials. Even if attackers manage to steal a password, MFA ensures they cannot access an account without the additional verification step. This reduces the effectiveness of phishing attempts that rely on obtaining login information, thus enhancing overall security.

Several participants discussed endpoint detection and response (EDR) systems as an important tool in combating phishing attacks. EDR solutions monitor devices for suspicious activities and respond in real time to mitigate threats. By providing detailed analytics on attack patterns, EDR can help institutions understand the tactics used by attackers and improve defenses against future phishing attempts. These systems enable rapid identification and neutralization of threats across all connected devices, increasing the overall resilience of an institution's cybersecurity infrastructure.

4.2.5 Cybersecurity policies or protocols that universities should enforce to better protect students from phishing threats should be discussed, along with how these policies can balance security and usability for students.

Many participants mentioned that universities should enforce mandatory cybersecurity training programs for students and staff, focusing on phishing awareness. Policies like enforcing multi-factor authentication (MFA) for university accounts and restricting access to official portals from unverified devices were also suggested. These measures aim to enhance security by making it harder for attackers to gain access. To balance security and usability, participants recommended user-friendly solutions, such as biometric authentication or password managers, which make security measures easier to use without compromising their effectiveness.

A key point raised by participants was the implementation of robust email filtering systems and real-time phishing alert mechanisms. Participants also suggested policies requiring regular password updates and safe browsing practices. These measures are essential for reducing phishing risks, but ensuring they don't disrupt usability is important. Using systems like single sign-on

(SSO) can help mitigate login fatigue while maintaining security. This highlights the need for universities to adopt practical security policies that do not overly burden students or staff.

Most participants agreed that simple, user-friendly solutions should be prioritized to avoid making cybersecurity measures too complicated for students. Policies such as cybersecurity reminders during daily logins, integrating phishing simulations, and offering clear guides or on-campus support for cybersecurity issues were common suggestions. These measures should be designed to seamlessly integrate into existing platforms, ensuring they don't slow down or overwhelm users. The focus here is on ensuring that students can easily access cybersecurity resources while maintaining their everyday activities.

4.2.6 The most common phishing techniques that target university students and why these methods are effective need to be identified.

Many participants mentioned phishing techniques that involve fake scholarship emails, bogus internship offers, or credential-stealing websites disguised as university portals. These methods are effective because students, especially those under pressure to secure scholarships or internships, may not take the time to verify the authenticity of such offers. The urgency and perceived importance of these opportunities make students more likely to fall for these scams. Phishing attempts like these exploit the emotional state of students and their desire to take advantage of opportunities, making them more vulnerable to attacks.

Another common phishing tactic mentioned was using fake account recovery emails or messages about unpaid tuition fees, which create a sense of urgency. These methods are effective because they pressure students into acting quickly without carefully assessing the situation. Attackers often mimic official university communication styles, which adds credibility to the phishing attempts. This technique works by leveraging emotional triggers, like the fear of losing access to accounts or facing penalties for overdue tuition, which causes students to react impulsively.

Participants also pointed out phishing attacks that exploit trust in familiar names or institutions, such as emails pretending to be from professors or administrative staff. These methods succeed because students trust messages from known sources like faculty members. Additionally, fake Wi-Fi login pages on campus are a common attack method, as students often connect to free or public networks without verifying their legitimacy. These attacks work because students are not cautious

when using familiar services or resources, making them more susceptible to falling for these types of scams.

4.2.7 Advice on how students can identify and avoid falling for phishing attacks, such as the one used in this Social experiment, should be provided.

Many participants emphasized the importance of carefully verifying the sender's email address and checking for signs like misspellings, suspicious links, and unexpected attachments. These red flags are common indicators of phishing attempts. If students are unsure, they should contact the institution or sender directly through official channels. This advice underscores the importance of caution and taking extra steps to verify the authenticity of messages, especially if they seem urgent or out of the ordinary.

A significant portion of responses focused on avoiding clicking on links in unsolicited emails. Instead, students should manually type URLs into their browsers or hover over links to verify their destination. Additionally, using strong, unique passwords and enabling multi-factor authentication (MFA) were strongly recommended for securing accounts. These actions add layers of security, making it more difficult for attackers to succeed in their attempts. This advice highlights the need for proactive measures, such as password management and MFA, to protect against phishing attacks.

Another common piece of advice was to trust one's instincts when something feels suspicious, like emails creating a sense of urgency or offering unrealistic rewards. Participants also recommended showing suspicious emails to someone more knowledgeable about technology before taking any action. This advice reinforces the idea that students should take a step back and think critically before responding to suspicious messages. Consulting with others or seeking help from the IT department can help prevent falling victim to phishing attacks.

4.3 DISCUSSION

Most participants agreed that while training programs are helpful in recognizing and avoiding common phishing attempts, they have limitations when it comes to advanced or targeted attacks like spear phishing. The need for additional technical measures alongside training was emphasized. This suggests that while awareness campaigns are useful for general phishing defense, they need to be supplemented with more sophisticated security measures to address highly targeted threats. More advanced defense techniques are necessary to ensure comprehensive protection against the full range of phishing attacks. This study agreed by (Basnet, 2008), who note that sophisticated attacks often require technical countermeasures in addition to training.

Another frequently mentioned advancement was multi-factor authentication (MFA). MFA strengthens security by adding another layer of verification, such as a text message code or biometric check, making it significantly harder for attackers to misuse stolen credentials. Even if attackers manage to steal a password, MFA ensures they cannot access an account without the additional verification step. This reduces the effectiveness of phishing attempts that rely on obtaining login information, thus enhancing overall security. (Chen and Guo, 2006) similarly highlight the role of enhanced authentication mechanisms, such as hardware devices or biometric checks, in thwarting attackers even when credentials are compromised. This demonstrates how MFA effectively disrupts the attack chain by ensuring that access cannot be gained without passing all verification steps.

Participants also pointed out phishing attacks that exploit trust in familiar names or institutions, such as emails pretending to be from professors or administrative staff. These methods succeed because students trust messages from known sources like faculty members. Additionally, fake Wi-Fi login pages on campus are a common attack method, as students often connect to free or public networks without verifying their legitimacy. These attacks work because students are not cautious when using familiar services or resources, making them more susceptible to falling for these types of scams. According to (Kirda and Kruegel, 2005), phishing attacks often use elements of trust, such as familiar names or organizational logos, to create a false sense of legitimacy.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Phishing is a type of online fraud where attackers try to trick people into giving away their personal information, such as passwords, credit card details, or bank account numbers. This is often done through fake emails, messages, or websites that look like they are from trusted companies. Phishing attacks present significant challenges due to their evolving and deceptive nature. These attacks are increasingly sophisticated, making them difficult to identify and combat effectively. Attackers often mimic trusted brands or individuals, creating highly convincing fake communications that are challenging for users to distinguish from legitimate ones. A critical challenge is the lack of user awareness, as many individuals fail to recognize phishing tactics or understand the importance of verifying links and emails before taking action.

The research strategy employed in this study involved a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from a social experiment with qualitative insights from interviews. The research design aimed to understand both the level of susceptibility and the reasons behind the students' actions when exposed to phishing attempts. The method of data collection consisted of three steps: first, a phishing WhatsApp message was crafted to mimic legitimate institutions, including suspicious links and requests for personal information; second, data was collected on students' interactions with the message, such as clicking links or providing information; and third, interviews were conducted to assess their understanding of phishing and the factors influencing their behavior.

Phishing attacks pose significant challenges due to their ability to evolve and adapt to new security measures. Attackers often create highly convincing fake emails, websites, or messages that closely

mimic legitimate ones, making them difficult to identify. The lack of awareness among users, especially students, further exacerbates the issue, as many are unfamiliar with the subtle signs of phishing, such as suspicious links or unexpected requests for personal information. Another challenge is the emotional manipulation used in phishing attacks, such as creating a sense of urgency or fear to pressure victims into acting quickly without verifying authenticity. Additionally, phishing tactics like fake scholarship emails and bogus account recovery requests exploit trust and familiarity, increasing their effectiveness.

To combat phishing, awareness and education are crucial. Students and staff should be trained to recognize phishing attempts by identifying red flags such as misspellings, suspicious email addresses, and unexpected attachments. Institutions should implement cybersecurity measures, such as multi-factor authentication (MFA), to add an extra layer of security to login processes. Regular phishing simulations can also help users practice identifying and avoiding scams in a controlled environment. Furthermore, organizations should deploy advanced tools like artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to detect suspicious patterns in emails and websites automatically. Finally, ensuring that users verify messages through official channels and avoid clicking on unsolicited links can significantly reduce the success of phishing attacks.

5.2 Recommendations

1. To Implement Comprehensive Cybersecurity Training
2. To Adopt Advanced Anti-Phishing Technologies
3. To Strengthen Institutional Cybersecurity Policies
4. To Collaborate with Cybersecurity Experts and Organizations

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APPENDIXES 1

1. How would you assess the level of cybersecurity awareness among undergraduate students, especially final-year students?
2. How effective do you think cybersecurity awareness campaigns or training programs are in reducing phishing attack success rates among institutions?
3. What are the latest advancements in technology that can help detect or mitigate phishing attacks?
4. Are there any cybersecurity policies or protocols you believe universities should enforce to better protect students from phishing threats? And how can these policies balance security and usability for students?
5. What are the most common phishing techniques that target university students? Why do you think these methods are effective?
6. What advice would you give to students on how to identify and avoid falling for phishing attacks like the one used in this Social experiment?

APPENDIXES 2

1. Sidee ayaad u qiimayn lahayd heerka wacyiga amniga internet-ka ee ardayda jaamacadda, gaar ahaan ardayda sannadka ugu dambeeya?
2. Sidee bay kula tahay in ololayaasha wacyigelinta amniga internet-ka ama barnaamijyada tababarka ay u yihiin kuwo wax ku ool ah si loo yareeyo heerka guusha weerarrada phishing-ka ee hay'adaha?
3. Waa maxay horumarrada ugu dambeeyay ee farsamada casriga ah ee ka caawin kara in la ogaado ama laga hortago weerarrada phishing-ka?
4. Ma jiraan siyaasad amni internet ama habraacyo aad aaminsantahay inay jaamacaduhu hirgelin karaan si si wanaagsan ardayda looga ilaaliyo khataraha phishing-ka? Sidee ayaase siyaasadahani ugu dheellitiri karaan amniga iyo fududeynta adeegsiga ardayda?
5. Waa maxay farsamooyinka phishing-ka ee ugu badan ee bartilmaameedsada ardayda jaamacadda? Maxaadse u malaynaysaa in hababkani ay yihiin kuwo waxtar leh?
6. Maxaad kula talin lahayd ardayda si ay u aqoonsadaan oo uga fogaadaan inay ku dhacaan weerarrada phishing-ka, sida midka lagu adeegsaday tijaabadan?

APPENDIXES 3

Hambalyo Hambalyo! 🎉

Fursad u hel Fully Funded Scholarship 2025! Sanadkan wax document ah lagama rabo ardayda – waxaa loo sameeyay sida waqtiyo nasiibka oo kale.

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